

Prevalence, Clinical Course and Outcomes of Pediatric Hematuria: A Prospective Analysis

Ashok Kumar Patel¹, Subhashini Trivedi², Chakresh Jain³, Kumar Shantnu⁴¹Assistant Professor, Department of Community Medicine, Dr. Sonelal Patel Autonomous State Medical College, Pratapgarh, Uttar Pradesh, India²Class 1 Gynecologist, District Hospital, Satna, Madhya Pradesh, India³Associate Professor, Department of Community Medicine, Shyam Shah Medical College, Rewa, Madhya Pradesh, India⁴Assistant Professor, Department of Pediatrics, Saraswati Institute of Medical Sciences, Hapur, Uttar Pradesh, India

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Corresponding Author: Dr. Kumar Shantnu

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Abstract:

Introduction: Hematuria, characterized by an elevated number of red blood cells (RBCs) in the urine, can manifest as either visible blood or be detectable only through microscopic examination, often identified incidentally. The incidence of microscopic hematuria is approximately 4–5% in routine clinical assessments of children aged 6–12 years. A thorough understanding of the clinical patterns and outcomes associated with hematuria is essential for optimizing management strategies in affected children. This study aimed to evaluate the outcomes of hematuria in children treated at an Indian tertiary care hospital.

Methods: A prospective follow-up study was conducted involving 178 children, aged between 1 month and 12 years, who were admitted with hematuria. Data were collected using a pre-designed and piloted questionnaire, including clinical history, physical examinations, relevant investigations, and follow-up assessments over a one-year period. A biopsy was performed on 35 patients by a qualified pathologist.

Results: Of the 178 children with hematuria, 43 had a history of renal disease, while 135 had no prior renal conditions. After one year of follow-up, 81.63% of those without previous renal issues experienced resolution of hematuria, while 18.37% had persistent renal impairment. In contrast, among those with pre-existing renal conditions, 75% (27) continued to exhibit renal problems. The condition was more prevalent in school-aged children with a higher incidence in females. The predominant cause was acute post-infectious glomerulonephritis, followed by IgA nephropathy and systemic lupus erythematosus.

Conclusion: Hematuria is a prevalent clinical issue, with majority of cases being identified at the time of admission. Following basic and relevant investigations, a clinical diagnosis can be established in most of the patients. The remaining require referral to subspecialties for further evaluation. Early renal biopsy is recommended for cases where indicated, to facilitate effective management. This approach will assist clinicians in providing enhanced care for children with hematuria.

Keywords: Glomerulonephritis; Hematuria; Renal biopsy; Childrens.

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Introduction

In pediatric populations, microscopic hematuria is commonly detected during routine health check-ups through dipstick tests or microscopy. It is found in approximately 0.52% of school-aged children without symptoms [1]. Children presenting with gross hematuria should undergo additional evaluation to rule out hypertension or renal dysfunction. Persistent hematuria is characterized by the presence of more than five red blood cells (RBCs) per high-power field (HPF). Urinary tract disorders typically manifest as hematuria, dysuria, and proteinuria. Even minute quantities of blood in

the urine can lead to macroscopic hematuria, whereas urine that appears clear might still contain an abnormal quantity of RBCs, known as microscopic hematuria [2]. There is no universally accepted definition of microscopic hematuria, but typically, more than 5–10 RBCs per high-power field in a centrifuged sample from 10 ml of freshly voided urine is considered significant. Hematuria is often an incidental finding in children, occurring in about 5–6% of the general population and 4% of school-aged children [3,4]. It is usually observed once but may appear in two out of three

consecutive samples in approximately 0.4% of cases. Spontaneous resolution occurs in 20–30% of children within a year, although it may also signify a serious underlying condition [5,6]. When a child presents with the first episode of hematuria without proteinuria, hypertension, or edema, initial evaluation should be performed, and the child should be closely monitored. Urine tests may be repeated after a week. Persistent hematuria with significant clinical findings necessitates further investigation, and a referral to a pediatric nephrologist should be considered if a serious renal issue is suspected [7].

Despite the variability in clinical presentation, diagnosis, and management of hematuria, recent guidelines provide evidence-based recommendations for managing glomerular disease. Additionally, advancements in histopathology and long-term outcomes of hematuria have prompted updates in treatment approaches. This study aimed to identify common causes of hematuria and to observe and analyze the progression and outcomes over a one-year period following the episode.

Material and Methods

A prospective follow-up study was conducted on 178 children aged 1 month to 12 years from January 2021 to July 2022. The study included both new-onset hematuria cases and children with pre-existing renal conditions presenting with hematuria. Those unwilling to participate or admitted to the ICU were excluded.

Data collection was facilitated using a pre-tested questionnaire, with detailed clinical histories obtained through interviews with mothers. Clinical details were recorded according to the questionnaire, and investigations were systematically planned and performed. Blood pressure was measured manually using a sphygmomanometer in line with WHO guidelines. Initial assessments were conducted in the ward, with follow-up visits scheduled at the outpatient clinic. A comprehensive medical history was documented, including past occurrences of

impetigo, pyoderma, sore throat, abdominal pain, and medication use (e.g., anticoagulants, aspirin). Family histories of hearing loss, chronic kidney disease, renal transplantation, and renal replacement therapy were also evaluated. Urine analysis was performed using both microscopic and dipstick methods. A thorough general and physical examination, including a genitourinary assessment, was conducted, followed by an extensive laboratory evaluation. Investigations included complete blood count, throat swab culture and sensitivity, complement component C3, sodium, potassium, serum creatinine, urea, 24-hour urine calcium-creatinine ratio, and protein-creatinine ratio.

During follow-up, repeat blood and urine examinations were conducted. Further evaluation included renal function tests and renal ultrasound when indicated. Additional diagnostic procedures such as micturating cystourethrogram, intravenous pyelogram, CT scan, and cystoscopy were performed as needed.

Renal biopsy was conducted in cases where indicated, including: persistent hematuria lasting more than 6 months without clinical or biochemical abnormalities, hematuria with clinical and biochemical anomalies not explained by existing tests, and progressive or persistent renal impairment, hypertension, persistent hypocomplementemia, and significant proteinuria. Biopsies were performed by experienced nephrologists and interpreted by a qualified pathologist.

Results

The study included 178 pediatric participants, with a higher proportion of females (56.75%, n=101) compared to males (43.26%, n=77). The age distribution revealed that the majority of the participants were between 6-12 years old (56.74%, n=101), followed by those aged 1-6 years (38.20%, n=68), and a small fraction under 1 year of age (5.06%, n=9).

Table 1: Age and gender distribution of study participants

Age Group	Male		Female		Total	
	n	%	n	%	n	%
<1 year	4	2.25	5	2.81	9	5.06
1–6 years	25	14.04	43	24.16	68	38.20
6–12 years	48	26.97	53	29.78	101	56.74
Total	77	43.26	101	56.75	178	100

The predominant cause of hematuria among the participants was post-infectious glomerulonephritis (PIGN), accounting for 59.55% (n=106) of the cases. Other notable causes included sepsis and urinary tract infections (UTI), each contributing to 11.8% (n=21) of the cases, while snake bites, idiopathic causes, and nephrolithiasis each represented less than 7% of the cases.

Table 2: Causes of hematuria in children

Cause	n	%
PIGN	106	59.55
Sepsis	21	11.8
UTI	21	11.8
Snake bite	12	6.74
Idiopathic	9	5.06
Nephrolithiasis	9	5.06
Total	178	100

Renal biopsy was performed on 62 participants (34.83% of the total cohort) to further investigate the underlying diagnosis of hematuria.

The most common diagnosis from the biopsies was IgA nephropathy (7.87%, n=14), followed by systemic lupus erythematosus (SLE) at 6.18% (n=11). Other diagnoses included diffuse

proliferative glomerulonephritis (DPGN) and acute tubular necrosis (ATN), each accounting for 3.93% (n=7) of the cases, and less frequently, hemolytic uremic syndrome (HUS), Henoch-Schönlein purpura (HSP), and focal segmental glomerulosclerosis (FSGS), each noted in 2.81% (n=5) of the biopsies.

Table 3: Diagnosis of hematuria by Renal Biopsy

Diagnosis	n	%
IgA nephropathy	14	7.87
SLE	11	6.18
DPGN	7	3.93
ATN	7	3.93
HUS	5	2.81
HSP	5	2.81
FSGS	5	2.81
PIGN	4	2.25
N / Thin BM disease	4	2.25
Total	62	34.83

The outcome data indicated that of the 178 participants, 24.16% (n=43) had a history of renal disease, while the remaining 75.84% (n=135) did not. Follow-up at one year showed that 55.06% (n=98) of the participants without a history of renal disease were monitored, compared to 20.22% (n=36) of those with a history. Persistent renal impairment was observed in 75% (n=27) of the

participants with a history of renal disease, compared to 18.37% (n=18) of those without.

Complete clearance of hematuria and normalization of renal function was achieved in 81.63% (n=80) of participants without a history of renal disease, while only 25% (n=9) of those with a history of renal disease experienced such outcomes.

Table 4: Outcome of the study participants

Parameter	History of renal disease		No history of renal disease	
	n	%	n	%
Total cases	43	24.16	135	75.84
F.up at 1 year	36	20.22	98	55.06
Persistent Renal impairment at 1 year	27	75	18	18.37
Complete Clearance of Hematuria and Normal renal function at 1 year	9	25	80	81.63

Discussion

In our study, the ratio of gross to microscopic hematuria was approximately 30:70. This distribution aligns with findings from Neiberger et al. and Kumar et al. [8,9], who reported similar trends. Hematuria was more prevalent among females and children aged between 5 and 15 years, a pattern consistent with observations in several other studies [10-12].

In cases of IgA nephropathy, the gender ratio was balanced, as also reported by Yoshikawa et al. [13]. Initially, we diagnosed majority of hematuria cases as post-streptococcal glomerulonephritis (PSGN), with most diagnosed based on clinical history alone, supported by preceding skin infections, upper respiratory tract infections, and hypocomplementemia. This finding is corroborated by Wyatt's study [14]. While many studies

identified urinary tract infections (UTIs) as the most common cause [15], only 11.80% of our cases were due to UTIs. Giare et al. [16] tracked 53 children with IgA nephropathy over 6.2 years, all showing mesangial IgA deposits. C3, IgG, and IgM deposits were found in 4, 3, and 2 patients, respectively, with mesangial hypercellularity in four cases. Stone et al. [17] observed similar results. Stages A and B correspond to the presence of gross or microscopic hematuria at onset, while stages C and D are associated with proteinuria or nephritic syndrome. Our cohort was classified as stage A or B, with no cases of chronic kidney disease or end-stage renal disease reported by the end of the follow-up. Yelsinkaya et al. [18] reviewed 50 children with membranoproliferative glomerulonephritis (MPGN), finding 20% with nephritis and 56% with nephrotic syndrome onset. Our study showed macroscopic hematuria predominantly in those with nephritic onset nephrotic syndrome. Following biopsy, we identified 7 cases of proliferative glomerulonephritis.

Among the 178 patients, 36 had recurrent or gross hematuria, and our working diagnosis was IgA nephropathy. Biopsy confirmed IgA nephropathy in 38.88% of cases, with 80% showing macroscopic hematuria and 20% microscopic hematuria. Kher et al. and Stone et al. [17,19] reported similar findings. Takahashi et al. [20] found comparable biopsy results in children under 3 years of age. In our study, 5 cases of focal segmental glomerulosclerosis (FSGS), 7 cases of diffuse proliferative glomerulonephritis (DPGN), 4 cases of thin basement membrane disease, and minor glomerular abnormalities in 5 cases were identified. The difference in etiology may be attributed to age variations, as Takahashi et al. focused on children younger than 3 years. Our study involved children aged 9–12 years with IgA nephropathy, PSGN, and systemic lupus erythematosus (SLE), and majority of post-infectious glomerulonephritis patients had proteinuria of 2+ and altered urea and creatinine levels. By the second visit, about 90% had resolved, with normal symptoms and complement levels after 8–12 weeks. However, in diffuse proliferative glomerulonephritis, 5 out of 7 cases had persistently decreased complement levels even after 3 months, while no hypocomplementemia was observed in IgA nephropathy.

Routine analyses included urea, electrolytes, urine routine, microscopy, culture, creatinine, and blood urea nitrogen, along with 24-hour urinary calcium, uric acid, and calcium-to-creatinine ratio tests. Leonard et al. [21] retrospectively studied 325 children with asymptomatic microscopic hematuria, all of whom had normal creatinine and electrolyte levels. Their study revealed renal ultrasound abnormalities in 18 patients, mild reflux

on voiding cystourethrogram in 9 patients, hypercalciuria in 29 patients, and urolithiasis in 9 patients. Positive family history was noted in 25% of patients. Leonard's study concluded that renal ultrasound, voiding cystourethrogram, cystoscopy, and kidney biopsy are generally not required for uncomplicated microscopic hematuria and are rarely indicative of serious disease. Strength of our study was that we conducted a comprehensive follow-up of 178 patients with hematuria, performing biopsies on 62 of them. This approach has significantly enhanced the management of hematuria, particularly in cases involving systemic lupus erythematosus (SLE) and IgA nephropathy. However, the follow-up duration was relatively brief. To fully evaluate long-term outcomes, it is necessary to continue monitoring these patients into adulthood.

Conclusion

Hematuria is a prevalent clinical issue, with majority of cases being identified at the time of admission. Following basic and relevant investigations, a clinical diagnosis can be established in most of the patients. The remaining requires referral to subspecialties for further evaluation. Early renal biopsy is recommended for cases where indicated, to facilitate effective management. Throughout the follow-up period, there were no deaths attributable to hematuria, even among children with significant renal lesions. The outcomes have improved significantly with the advent of newer diagnostic techniques and treatments.

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